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EVALUATION OF 2.5 KILOWATTS GENERATING PLANT USING COOKING GAS (LPG) AS FUEL

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ABSTRACT

Liquefied Petroleum Gas is a flammable hydrocarbon gas which is produced during natural gas processing and petroleum refining. The important of using Liquefied Petroleum Gas is more than employing as cooking fuel in the developing countries. The underutilization of this clean and environmental friendly gas had led to this study to evaluate its usefulness in powering household electric generator. This research work was aimed at investigating and evaluating to prove for the existence of the consumption rate of the Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) compare with that of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) fuel to power the electric generator. The gasoline carburettor was replaced with hybrid dual carburettor which allowed the direct flow of PMS and LPG respectively. The gas pressure regulator was fitted to the gas cylinder tank for the regulation of LPG pressure and flow rate. The results showed that the LPG average consumption time was 2.32 hr/kg and 1.25 hr/litre while PMS average consumption time was 1.48 hr/litre and 2.00 hr/kg. LPG had a lower noise, very low sooth than the PMS and also had a lower consumption rate than PMS.

KEYWORDS: Consumption Time; Electric generator; Liquefied Petroleum Gas; Premium Motor Spirit.

INTRODUCTION

Cooking gas which is liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) is a mixture of light hydrocarbons. Liquefied Petroleum Gas describes as a flammable hydrocarbon gas which is produced during natural gas processing and petroleum refining, which can also be produced either from gas wells or in conjunction with crude oil production (Ross, 2017). In reality, LPG is a valuable co-product produced from gas fields and crude oil refining (Eric, 2019; SustyVibes, 2017). Because of the gaseous nature of this fuel, it has to be stored in a compressed gaseous state in a gas cylinders as liquefied state (Nigeria's Distributed Energy Revolution, 2017). ESMAP (2004) published that the commercial grade LPG is primarily a mixture of butane and propane and the ratio of these constituents can vary widely. The commercial and domestic LPG composition includes propane, butane and mixtures of these gases and supported (Eric 2019; Thompson, 2015). In different countries, the commercial and domestic LPG composition can be propane, butane or propane-butane blends.

According to ESMAP (2004), it was stated that in Nigeria this Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) constituents are primarily mixtures of propane and butane gases. However, the LPG is a versatile fuel with a wide range of other uses in household, commercial and industrial energy applications. It is used principally as a cooking fuel in households and in catering. In a world like today, where everything runs on electricity. It is almost impossible to live without power, thus necessitating the invention of an alternative source of power known as the "Generator". The problem of power outage and irregularity in supply of power in Nigeria today is no-longer news to the citizens. This problem as resulted in a negative economic down turn, resulting in the relocation of many industries out of Nigeria into other-neighbouring countries. The

problem of power failure as also shown in affecting the prices of goods and services in Nigeria today. The Generator has been an excellent source of backup power for many decades.

WLPGA (2017) reported that the International Energy Agency (IEA) anticipates a 50% growth in the demand for natural gas in the period 2016 to 2040 with much of this growth associated with electricity generation. It stated that, there was growing evidence to suggest that LPG would have an important role to play within the global Power Generation sector in the next 10 to 20 plus years. It was also declared that the use of LPG as a 'bridging' fuel would present a strong opportunity in the next 10 to 20 years. LPG is generally considered as one of the cleanest energy source because it does not pollute the soil, water and groundwater. The LPG fuels are readily available, low environmental impact and high energy yield and calorific value. They are flammable, but are not toxic, low sulphur content and a complete combustion, with small amounts of residues, contribute to reducing the environmental impact caused by pollution resulting from their combustion, promoting better air quality and a reduction in emissions of greenhouse gases emissions. The absence of dust, soot, heavy metals during their combustion of LPG also allows a substantial reduction in maintenance costs of any equipment that used it as fuel (Green Power Systems, 2019).

Cooking gas can be used to power regular generators. It was a fact true and possible to have a generator run on the same cooking gas we use in our kitchen. The use of natural gas and for generators has been on for a while in the developed countries, but this was in comparison with diesel generators implying that some generators are originally built to run with natural gas.

When using LPG, there are less emissions, less noise and they are relatively cheaper to use, but the scary

disadvantage is the possibility of a gas leak (SustyVibes, 2017).

What this new technology does is to remove the inbuilt carburettor that comes with the regular generators and use a hybrid dual fuel carburettor that allows gasoline (Premium Motor Spirit) and LPG to power the engine in order to produce electricity independently. If this technology gets along in the market due to its viability, it would have good future prospect in developing country. These generators would offer several advantages and the market would be more and more interested with these following features in terms of low operating costs, environmentally-friendly emissions, lower noise level compared to diesel engines and higher flexibility in generator location. LPG comparatively has lower costs, environment friendly, lower emissions, lower noise level good flexibility to other fossil fuels (Green Power Systems, 2019).

LPG is a mixture of about 60 % Propane and 40% Butane. Propane and butane are both safe, non-toxic, clean-burning fuels that are a great source of energy. With a lower carbon content than oil, gasoline, diesel, kerosene and ethanol, propane and butane gas contain significantly less greenhouse gas emissions per productivity unit compared to other fuels. Propane and butane gas contain significantly less greenhouse gas emissions per productivity unit compared to other fuels (Budget Propane, 2019; Quora, 2018, Smith, 2015). LPG is a colourless and odourless gas in its natural state. Odourant is added for safety (Eric, 2019).

Wuyan et al., (2014) performed experiment on conversion of gasoline generator to biogas fuel to power the generating plant using 80 % biogas and 20 % LPG. The studied showed that at the ratio 4 to 1 composition of the fuel mixture, the generator run with maximum speed of 3600 rpm. The researchers reported that the maximum value of the engine speed by using gasoline fuel is 3600 rpm.

Nwaokocha and Okezie (2016) studied on conversion of petrol generator to propane type of liquefied petroleum gas. The researchers identified that at no load condition gasoline flow rate was 0.5 – 0.52 kg/h and LPG flow rate was 0.30 – 0.32 kg/h. LPG would be currently the most viable fuel option for 15 % of the world population that lacks electricity according to Thompson (2015) cited in SE4All. GTF (2015). LPG is a clean burning gas as well as other kinds of gaseous fuels (biogas and natural gas) needs to be prioritized (Thompson, 2015). Liquid fuel is a combustible and energy-generating molecules that can be harnessed to create mechanical energy (Lithopsian, 2020). Production of LPG through the conversion refinery operations as shown in Figure 1.

This research work was aimed at investigating and evaluating to prove for the existence of the consumption rate of the Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) compare with that of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), as well as testing

it reliability, efficiency and duration of time taken for each fuel component to power the electric generator.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for this research were as followed: Gasoline electric generator with prime mover model of GX-160, Hybrid dual fuel carburettor, 5kilogram gas cylinder tank, Gas hose of model AM A-Z (8*15), Gas pressure regulator of model Type GF-50 with specification maximum inlet pressure of 10bar and with outlet pressure of 30 mbar at mass flow rate of 1.5 kg/h.

Gasoline Electric Generator: Electric generator is any machine that converts mechanical energy to electricity for transmission and distribution over power lines to domestic, commercial, and industrial customers (Slemon, 2013). Electric generator for the Experimental Evaluation as shown in Plate 1.

Carburettor: The gasoline carburettor is a device for supplying a spark-ignition engine with an introduction of fuel into the airstream and the mixture of fuel and air flow into the engine. The choke is a device that can partially block air from getting into the carburettor. An airflow carries the atomized gasoline to the engine's cylinders, where the gas is ignited (Cromer & Proctor, 2013; Fetherston, 2009). Hybrid dual and schematic operations of gasoline carburettor as shown in Plate 2 and Figure 2.

LPG Pressure Regulator: Pressure regulator is a device that maintains the pressure of LPG from the inlet and keep this pressure within the prescribed range and acceptable limits that can be tolerated by the prime mover using the fuel. Gas pressure regulator used for the control of the LPG into the electric generator as shown in Plate 3.

Gas Cylinder Tank: Gas cylinder tank is a storage of the volume of LPG needed to satisfy the demands of fuel in the prime mover of the electric generator (Nathanson, 2013). Gas cylinder tank used for the storage of the LPG for the fuelling of the electric generator as shown in Plate 4.

METHODS

Elepaq gasoline generator manufactured by Constant was used for this research with a model number of EC5800CX. The generator comprised of a single cylinder, 4-stroke, spark ignition engine of rated output capacity of 2.2 to 2.5 kW, 220 to 240V, 50Hz electricity. The gasoline carburettor was replaced with hybrid dual carburettor which allowed the direct flow of PMS and LPG respectively. The gas pressure regulator was fitted to the gas cylinder tank for the regulation of LPG pressure and flow rate. PMS feed flow supply was measured volumetrically using calibrated plastic bucket container and LPG feed flow supply was measured using sensitive weighing balance respectively. LPG and PMS were obtained from Federal Polytechnic, Ado venture in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The experimental set up as shown in Plate 5.

The PMS was used to power the electric generator range from volume of one litre to five litres of fuel. Then, the LPG was also used to experiment the duration of hour that the fuel would be exhausted ranging from 1 kilogram to five kilograms. The electric generator was tested on no-load for the range of quantity of PMS and LPG respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results presented in this research from the experiment performed on electric generator at no-load highlights in benefits of LPG compared to PMS were estimated. Chemical reaction between substances is usually including oxygen and accompanied by the generation of heat and light in the form of flame. The products obtained from a given set of reactants depend on the conditions under which a chemical reaction occurs (Kondratiev, 2013; Campbell, 2009). Ignition is a process of igniting a combustible substance and occurs when the temperature of a substance is raised to the point at which its molecules will react spontaneously with oxygen and it begins to burn. Combustion is a process of rapid oxidation and burning of a substance with simultaneous evolution of heat with light, where combustion is initiated by a spark the volatile fuels such as gasoline (PMS) or gas (LPG) required 16 to 23 kg of air for complete combustion of 1 kg of fuel (Treybal, 2009). Eric (2019) elucidated that the percentages of LPG that must be presented in LPG/air mixture is between 2.15 % and 9.6 % of the total LPG/air mixture for it to be combustible. The typical internal cylinder of a gasoline engine as shown in Figure 3.

The results obtained from the experiment of using PMS and LPG under the condition of no-load gave a chemical reaction of the combustion of PMS and LPG as given in equation 1 to 4. The combustion equation to determine the amount of air to support the combustion as given as follows: The complete combustion equation (Eric, 2019).

Table 1 presented some properties of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) and Gasoline (PMS). LPG density varying between 500 to 550 kg/m³ according to the report of Bulletin (2020).

The results obtained from the experiment using PMS and LPG as fuel to power the electric generator under the condition of no-load were presented in Table 2 to 4. The result for both mass and volume against consumption time for PMS was graphically presented to highlight its trend as shown in Figure 4. The result for both mass and volume against consumption time for LPG was

graphically presented to highlight its trend as shown in Figure 5. The result for both the mass of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) and volume of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) used against consumption time was graphically presented to highlight their comparison as shown in Figure 6.

The result obtained after the experimental testing, shows that using cooking gas (LPG) as proven to be more durable, low level. Because it offered longer period of power supply compared to when PMS was used to power the electric generator. Using LPG gave produce low level of noise and the fume produce is non-toxic compare to PMS. The cost of running the electric generator by using LPG is very moderate. The experiment enlightened in such a way that if the generator is not in use for days the LPG will still in the storage as the same quantity unlike petrol which is very volatile. The results showed that the LPG average consumption time was 2.32 hr/kg and 1.25 hr/litre while PMS average consumption time was 1.48 hr/litre and 2.00 hr/kg.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The investigation and evaluation of comparing the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) with premium motor spirit (PMS) established that the LPG was found to be more efficient than the PMS. LPG had a lower noise, very low sooth than the PMS and also had a lower consumption rate than PMS. It was deduced that the LPG average consumption time was 2.32 hr/kg and 1.25 hr/litre while PMS average consumption time was 1.48 hr/litre and 2.00 hr/kg.

Therefore, it has to be recommended that the development and environmental benefits of LPG as a fuel for powering domestic generating plant be strongly embraced and promoted in developing countries. Since, the convectional fossil fuels pose high treat to human health in the society due to high pollutants given off during the combustion process to the environment.

REFERENCES

Barnett, J. R. (2009). "Fire". Microsoft Encarta Premium, Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington, USA.

Budget Propane (2019). "Is Butane Safer than Propane" Ontario. Retrieved from <https://www.budgetpropaneontario.com>

Bulletin (2020). Convert and Calculate. Online Conversion Forum. Retrieved from <https://www.onlineconversion.com>

Campbell, J. A. (2009). "Chemical Reaction". Microsoft Encarta Premium, Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington D. C., USA.

Cromer, O. C., & Proctor, C. L. (2013) "Gasoline Engine". Encycloepadia Britannica Article, Encycloepadia Britannica Ultimate Reference Suite, Chicago, USA.

Eric Hahn (2019). LPG Properties & LPG Composition. Elgas-LPG Gas Blog. Elgas Ltd. Retrieved from <https://www.elgas.com.au>

- ESMAP (2004). Nigerian LP Gas Sector Improvement Study. World Bank / Energy Sector Management Assistance Programme (ESMAP) CIS LPG Consultants. The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank, 1818 H Street, N.W. Washington, D.C. 20433, U.S.A.
- Fetherston, D. (2009). "Carburetor." Microsoft Encarta Premium, Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington D. C., USA.
- Green Power Systems (2019). Green Power Generators. Green Power Systems srl, Green Power Company Edition. Localita Maiano sn/61028, Caprazzino di Sassocorvaro (PU) Italy. Retrieved from <https://www.greenpowergen.com>
- Kondratiev, V. N. (2013). "Combustion". Encyclopaedia Britannica Article, Encyclopaedia Britannica Ultimate Reference Suite, Chicago, USA.
- Nathanson, J. A. (2013). "Storage". Encyclopaedia Britannica Article, Encyclopaedia Britannica Ultimate Reference Suite, Chicago, USA.
- Nigeria's Distributed Energy Revolution (2017). Expanding Clean Energy Access through Rural Women-Led MSMEs.
- Nwaokocha, C. N., & Okezie, S. U. (2016). A Conversion of Petrol Generator to Enable the Use of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (Propane). *Nigerian Journal of Oil and Gas Technology*, 1-6.
- Quora (2018). "Can you use LPG in place of propane" Retrieved from <https://www.quora.com>
- Ross, R. (2017). Emissions and Performance of Liquefied Petroleum Gas as a Transportation Fuel: A Review, Center for Alternative Fuels, Engines, and Emissions, West Virginia University, USA.
- SE4All. GTF (2015). Progress towards Sustainable Energy. Second Edition, World Bank. Lithopsian (2020). LP Gas Fundamentals, NIOSH Pocket Guide to Chemical Hazards Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, USA.
- Slemon, G. R. (2013). "Electric Generator". Encyclopaedia Britannica Article, Encyclopaedia Britannica Ultimate Reference Suite, Chicago, USA.
- Smith, K. R. (2015). Changing Paradigms in Clean Cooking. *EcoHealth*, 12 (1), 196-199.
- Solomon, L. H., & Waddams, A. L. (2013). Petroleum Refining, Encyclopaedia Britannica Article, Encyclopaedia Britannica Ultimate Reference Suite, Chicago, USA.
- Susty Vibes (2017). Energy Power: My Thoughts on the Use of Cooking Gas for Generators. Retrieved from <https://www.sustyvibes.com>
- The Engineering Tool Box (2020). "Fuels". Fuels Higher and Lower Calorific Values. Resources, Tool and Basic Information for Engineering and Design of Technical Applications. Retrieved from <https://www.EngineeringToolBox.com>
- Thompson, L. M. (2015). Cooking with Gas: How Children in the Developing World Benefit From Switching to LPG. WLPGA, 182, Avenue Charles de Gaulle 92200 Neuilly-Sur-Seine, France. Retrieved from <https://www.wlpga.org>
- Treybal, R. E. (2009). "Combustion". Microsoft Encarta Premium, Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington D. C., USA.
- Wayan, S., Tjokorda, G. T. N., Ketut, A. A., Dewa, N. K. P. N., & Wayan, E. P. P. (2014). Simple conversion method from gasoline to biogas fueled small engine to powered electric generator. *Energy Procedia* 52, 626-632.
- World LPG Association, WLPGA (2017). Global LPG Power Generation Market Development & Recommendations for Future Growth. The World LPG Association (WLPGA). Dublin, Ireland. Retrieved from <https://www.wlpga.org>

Plate 1: Electric generator for the Experimental Evaluation

Plate 2: Hybrid Dual Fuel Carburettor

Plate 3: LPG Gas Pressure Regulator

Plate 4: LPG Gas Cylinder Tank

Plate 5: Experimental Set-up

Figure 1: Conversion Refinery Operations (Solomon & Waddams, 2013).

Figure 2: A Simple Schematic Carburettor (Cromer & Proctor, 2013)

Figure 3: Typical Internal Cylinder of a Gasoline Engine (Cromer and Proctor, 2013)

Figure 4: Mass and Volume of PMS against Consumption Time.

Figure 5: Mass and Volume of LPG against Consumption Time.

Figure 6: LPG in Mass (kilogram) and PMS in Volume (litre) against Consumption Time (hour)

Table 1: Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) and Gasoline (PMS) Properties

Ambient Conditions: 15 °C (293 K); 1 bar (100 kPa)	LPG	Gasoline
Density	537 kg/m ³	737 kg/m ³
Calorific Value	49.3MJ/kg	46.4 MJ/kg
LPG Ignition Temperature in Air	470 °C to 550 °C	280 °C
LPG Flash Point	-104 °C to -60 °C	-43 °C
Anti-knock (Octane Rating/Number) - RON	102 to 108	87 to 100

The Engineering ToolBox, 2020; Eric, 2019; Solomon and Waddams, 2013; Barnett, 2009

Table 2: Time for the running of the quantity of Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) fuel

S/N	Gasoline PMS (Litre)	Gasoline PMS (kg)	Time Spent (Hour)
1	1.00	0.74	1.041
2	2.00	1.47	3.016
3	3.00	2.21	4.524
4	4.00	2.95	6.052
5	5.00	3.69	7.540

Table 3: Time for the running of the quantity of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) Fuel

S/N	Cooking Gas LPG (kg)	Cooking Gas LPG (Litre)	Time Spent (Hour)
1	1.00	1.86	2.318
2	2.00	3.72	4.636
3	3.00	5.59	6.954
4	4.00	7.45	9.272
5	5.00	9.31	11.590

Table 4: Consumption Time per hour using PMS and LPG as Fuel

PMS in Volume (Litre) and LPG in Mass (Kg)	Time Spent (Hour) by PMS	Time Spent (Hour) by LPG
1	1.041	2.318
2	3.016	4.636
3	4.524	6.954
4	6.052	9.272
5	7.54	11.59

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